

Practice Abstract no. 33

Consumers & citizens' concerns regarding personal data sharing

The #Data4Food Cluster comprising the [DRG4Food](#), [FOODITY](#), [FoodDataQuest](#), and [SOSFood](#) projects organised a joint workshop in June 2025 to discuss challenges, enablers, and gains related to data sharing and AI-driven solutions for sustainable food systems. Two breakout room sessions explored perspectives from both consumers/citizens and industry/food system actors on data sharing and AI in food systems.

This practice abstract discusses consumers/ citizens' main concerns regarding sharing of personal data.

- **Tracking abuse/ theft**, which includes general abuse of tracking and tracking leading to the theft of data.
- **Privacy breaches and misuse of data**, which encompasses privacy breaches, misuse of personal data, profiling, password leakage, and the resale of (personal) data.
- **Third-party data sharing issues**, which focuses on concerns about data being used by third parties, including to third parties beyond the original country (i.e. international data transfer issues).
- **Damaging marketing and over consumption**, which relates to the increased consumption of products and services, driven by intensive marketing strategies, and the inherent sharing of data.

The aforementioned information is available and further detailed in the joint report developed by the #Data4Food Cluster "What Helps and What Hurts When Sharing Data for Sustainable Food Solutions."

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